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PREDICTING WATER BALANCE DYNAMICS FOR SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE IN THANJAVUR, TAMIL NADU: A MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH USING MODIS AND CHIRPS DATASETS

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ABSTRACT

In southern India, Thanjavur serves as a significant rice-producing region within Tamil Nadu, capable of yielding two to three rice harvests annually. This investigation examined the monthly water balance in Thanjavur from 2010 to 2022 utilizing Machine Learning (ML) on the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform, employing JavaScript. Essential satellite data sources included MOD16A2.061 for ET at 500 meters resolution and CHIRPS for Precipitation at 5566 meters resolution. The study considered elements such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, runoff, and storage fluctuations. To determine the monthly average water balance, data was restructured to compute Q and ΔS at the pixel level before aggregating to the basin scale. Vegetation and drought indicators, including MSI (Moisture Stress Index) and EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index), were evaluated for monthly mean values to assess vegetation health and water stress. Superimposing land cover with these indices revealed which land cover types were most affected by water scarcity. Average P and ET for each land cover category were determined using a land cover map, indicating that cropland and agriculture consume the most water. The study analyzed the monthly water balance for cropland, forest, grassland, and urban areas, demonstrating significant water usage by forest and cropland during dry periods. Grassland, being less extensive, exhibited reduced water consumption in the dry season. Furthermore, an ML model forecasted future water balance trends, facilitating the comprehension of upcoming patterns. This consistent growth suggests improved water availability, potentially enhancing agricultural planning, optimizing crop development, and strengthening water resource management for sustained productivity.

Keywords: Rice-producing, Thanjavur, Evapotranspiration (ET), Precipitation(P), Machine Learning Google Earth Engine, Water balance(WB)